

collapsed after that emigration.

Population density was highest at 9-11 WT, regardless of population pattern. Hopperburn depended on the nymph density at its climax. Most hopperburn-causing nymphs were

considered to have come from the brachypterous females emerging 6-8 WT. Those brachypterous females emerged from the progeny of macropterous immigrants arriving at 315 WT. The densities of macropterous

females at 3-5 WT and of brachypterous females at 6-8 WT, seem to be important parameters for predicting hopperburn on paddy crops at ripening. \mathcal{J}

Host range and biology of three rice caseworms

N. Chantaraprapha, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand; and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Three pyralid caseworms are commonly collected in light traps at IRRI.

Nymphula depunctalis (Guenée) is a known pest of rice. The pest status of *Parponyx* (= *Nymphula*) *fluctuosalis* (Zeller) and *Parponyx* (= *Nymphula*) *diminutalis* (Snellen) was determined using rice and 61 ricefield weeds as hosts. Vegetative stage plants were used as caseworm attacks occur only during the first month after transplanting.

The plants were collected at IRRI and offered as food to newly hatched first-instar larvae. During the first round of screening, free-choice tests reduced the number of potential hosts to 28 (Table 1). Caseworm development was further evaluated in no-choice tests from the first larval stage through adulthood.

On all development parameters, rice was the most nutritious host; 85% larvae pupated and 67% emerged as adults. The polyphagous rice caseworm developed on 23 plant species representing 18 genera and 2 families. Survivorship to adulthood was low (2-36%) on the 22 nonrice hosts.

The larval growth index includes two developmental parameters: survival and days to pupation. A high growth index occurs with high survival and short developmental period. More than 20% of adults reared on *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Polytrias amaura*, *Chrysopogon aciculatus*, *Leersia hexandra*, and *Ischaemum muticum* emerged.

Neither *P. fluctuosalis* nor *P.*

Table 1. Host plant range of 3 species of caseworms found in ricefields.^a IRRI, 1983.

Plant ^b	Larval growth index ^c		
	<i>N. depunctalis</i>	<i>P. fluctuosalis</i>	<i>P. diminutalis</i>
Poaceae: Gramineae			
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	6.35 a	0	0
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	1.92 b	1.5 c	0
<i>Polytrias amaura</i>	1.51 c	0	0
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	1.50 c	0.6 f	0
<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i>	1.43 cd	0	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	1.31 d	0	0
<i>Ischaemum muticum</i>	1.11 e	0	0
<i>Phragmites vulgaris</i>	1.04 ef	0	0
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	1.01 ef	0	0
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	0.94 fg	0.3 gh	0
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	0.83 gh	0	0
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	0.75 hi	0	0
spp. <i>hispidula</i>			
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	0.74 ij	0	0
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	0.58 ijk	0	0
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	0.55 jk	0	0
<i>Chloris barbata</i>	0.43 klm	0	0
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	0.28 mn	0	0
<i>Panicum repens</i>	0.25 n	0	0
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	0.20 n	0.6 f	0.1 e
Cyperaceae			
<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i>	0.74 ij	2.4 b	0.2 e
<i>C. rotundus</i>	0.46 kl	0.7 f	0.9 d
<i>C. difformis</i>	0.36 lmn	0.2 h	0.8 d
<i>Fimbristylis miliaceae</i>	0.30 lmn	0.4 g	0.3 e
Hydrocharitaceae			
<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i>	0	3.3 a	5.2 a
<i>Blyxa echinosperma</i>	0	0.9 e	0.8 d
<i>Ottelia alismoides</i>	0	0.1 f	2.0 c
Characeae			
<i>Chara vulgaris</i>	0	1.4 cd	2.6 b
Commelinaceae			
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	0	1.3 d	0.7 d

^a Av of 4 replications, 25 larvae/replication. ^b These plants were not hosts to any caseworm species: *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Amaranthus spinosus* (Amaranthaceae); *Pistia stratiotes* (Araceae); *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Eclipta prostrata*, *Tridax procumbens* (Asteraceae); *Azolla caroliniana*, *Azolla microphylla*, *Azolla pinnata* (Azollaceae); *Cleome rutidosperma* (Capparidaceae); *Pithophora* sp. (Cladophoraceae); *Commelina benghalensis* (Commelinaceae); *Ipomoea aquatica*, *Ipomoea triloba* (Convolvulaceae); *Cyperus iria* (Cyperaceae); *Euphorbia hirta*, *Phyllanthus niruri* (Euphorbiaceae), *Marsilia minuta* (Marsileaceae); *Mimosa pudica* (Mimosaceae); *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Onagraceae); *Aeschynomene indica*, *Calopogonium mucunoides*, *Macroptilium lathyroides* (Papilionaceae); *Ceratopteris thalictroides* (Parkeriaceae); *Peperomia pellucida* (Piperaceae); *Imperata cylindrica*, *Polytrias amaura*, *Rottboellia exaltata* (Poaceae); *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Monochoria vaginalis* (Pontederiaceae); *Portulaca oleraceae* (Portulacaceae); *Borreria ocymoides*, *Hedyotis biflora* (Rubiaceae); *Lindernia anagallis* (Scrophulariaceae); *Sphenoclea zeylanica* (Sphenocleaceae). ^c Growth index = pupation (%) divided by larval development (d).

diminutalis survived on rice. They are true aquatic caseworms (they remain underwater during their entire larval period). *N. depunctalis* larvae are

semiaquatic, ascending rice plants at night to feed.

The most suitable host of *P. fluctuosalis* and *P. diminutalis* was the

aquatic weed *Hydrilla verticillata*, which occurs in more permanent bodies of water such as reservoirs and canals. Several of the needle-shaped leaves are tied together by the larva to make a case. The rearing method for both aquatic caseworms was less than ideal on *Hydrilla*; only 40-50% survived to adulthood. They pupate out of water on plant vegetation.

The host range of *P. diminutalis* was three times less than *N. depunctalis* and overlapped entirely with *P. fluctuosalis*, which accepted three more plant hosts. All three caseworms shared five host plants, four of them sedges: *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *C. rotundus*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*.

All these caseworms are similar in size and fertility (Table 2). *P. diminutalis* has four larval instars, one less than *P. fluctuosalis* and *N.*

Table 2. Life histories of *P. diminutalis* and *P. fluctuosalis* on *Hydrilla verticillata* and of *N. depunctalis* on *Oryza sativa* (IR36).^aIRRI headhouse, 1983.

Character	<i>P. diminutalis</i>	<i>P. fluctuosalis</i>	<i>N. depunctalis</i>
Fertility (no. eggs/female) ^b	130	125	117
Egg incubation period (d)	5.5	4.5	4.5
Larval developmental period (d)			
First stadium	2.5	3.0	3.5
Second stadium	3.3	3.9	3.8
Third stadium	3.3	4.5	4.1
Fourth stadium	4.0	4.5	4.5
Fifth stadium	— ^c	5.3	5.8
Pupal period (d)	6.9	9.6	7.9
Male longevity (d)	4.2	3.1	3.0
Female longevity (d)	4.3	3.9	5.0
Sex ratio (male:female)	1:1.5	1:1.2	1:1
Developmental period from egg to adult ^d (d)	29.8	39.2	39.1

^aAv of 20 replications except when indicated otherwise. ^b Av of 5 pairs. ^c No fifth stadium. ^d Female.

depunctalis; matures about 10 d earlier than the 2; and has a longer egg incubation period. The sex ratio favored the development of females in *P. diminutalis* and *P. fluctuosalis*,

probably because of the lack of a better rearing method. The present rearing method seemed to favor larger individuals, which were mostly females. ♀

Chromosomes of the primary spermatocytes of *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stål)

R. C. Saxena, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), Kenya, and International Rice Research Institute (IRRI); and A. A. Barrion, Institute of Biological Sciences, University of the Philippines at Los Baños

The testicular primary spermatocytes of newly emerged green leafhopper *N. nigropictus* contained first meiotic holocentric chromosomes. At diakinesis (Fig. 1a), the genomic complement consisted of 7 bivalent autosomes plus a univalent X-chromosome. Therefore, the diploid chromosome number of male *N. nigropictus* is $2n = 15 (7II_A + XO)$.

The prospective spermatozoa are of 2 types: $n = 8 (7I_A + X)$ and $n = 7 (7I_A + 0)$. During metaphase I (Fig. 1b), the heterochromatic X-body can be seen isolated from autosomes at the equatorial plate.

Pachytene analysis showed that the whole genome of males consisted of eight linkage groups (Fig. 2). The longest autosome was almost double

1. Chromosomes of male *N. nigropictus* at a) diakinesis showing $2n = 15$, b) metaphase I. Spontaneous aberration may result in c) an agmatoploid cell with $2n = 19 (9II + X)$. IRRI, 1985-86. The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification 1500X (oil immersion).

the shortest. The relative mean lengths of chromosomes ranged from 0.062 to 0.165. The sex chromosome measured 0.062 and the autosome with the nucleolar organizing region (NOR) 0.155.

The chromosomes condensed maximally during prometaphase into dumbbells of bivalents measuring 3.9μ , 3.3μ (NOR), 2.7μ , 2.5μ , 2.4μ , 2.1μ , 2.0μ , and 1.6μ (X). Their

2. Camera lucida drawing of pachytene chromosomes of *N. nigropictus* and their idiogram. IRRI, 1985-86. The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification 1250X (oil immersion).

corresponding chromosome volumes were $0.025 \mu^3$, $0.015 \mu^3$, $0.009 \mu^3$, $0.007 \mu^3$, $0.007 \mu^3$, $0.004 \mu^3$, $0.003 \mu^3$, and $0.001 \mu^3$.

The mean meiotic index approximated 0.61, the mean number of dividing spermatocytes was 227, the number of nondividing cells was 147.

Of 100 cells at diakinesis, 24% contain a reduced number of bivalents and 5% possessed an increased number of chromosomes (Fig. 1c). ♀